

ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

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COOPERATION BETWEEN STATES IN THE FIELD OF COUNTERACTION EXTREMISM

ANNOTATION

The article highlights the problems of the spread of extremism in the world. An analysis of the practice of individual international organizations and foreign states in countering extremism was carried out. Proposals have been formulated regarding the formation of international systems for countering extremism.

Key words: extremism, intergroup conflict, countering extremism, protection of human rights and freedoms, society and the state, national security.

ЭКСТРЕМИЗМГА ҚАРШИ КУРАШИШ СОҲАСИДА ДАВЛАТЛАР ЎРТАСИДАГИ ҲАМКОРЛИК

АННОТАЦИЯ

Мақолада дунёда экстремизмнинг тарқалиши муаммолари ёритилган. Айрим халқаро ташкилотлар ва хорижий давлатларнинг экстремизмга қарши курашиш амалиёти таҳлил қилинган. Экстремизмга қарши курашишнинг халқаро тизимларини шакллантириш бўйича таклифлар ишлаб чиқилган.

Калит сўзлар: ekstremizm, guruhlararo nizolar, ekstremizmga qarshi kurashish, inson huquq va erkinliklarini, jamiyat va davlatni himoya qilish, milliy xavfsizlik.

СОТРУДНИЧЕСТВО ГОСУДАРСТВ В СФЕРЕ ПРОТИВОДЕЙСТВИЯ ЭКСТРЕМИЗМУ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье освещены проблемы распространения экстремизма в мире. Осуществлен анализ практики отдельных международных организаций и иностранных государств по противодействию экстремизму. Сформулированы предложения относительно формирования международных систем противодействия экстремизму.

Ключевые слова: экстремизм, межгрупповой конфликт, противодействие экстремизму, защита прав и свобод человека, общества и государства, национальная безопасность.

The ethnic, cultural, religious, linguistic, ideological and national diversity of humanity is a unique factor in its development; it enables individuals to unite according to certain characteristics into stable groups, develop common values and social norms, developing and protecting themselves and their own achievements in various spheres of public life.

Today, joining a certain social group is an objective process of personal self-identification, a consequence of the evolution of society. At the same time, such diversity is a source of social conflicts, especially intergroup conflicts, which, as history shows, has repeatedly led and leads to numerous casualties, the destruction of certain segments of the population or even nations.

By its nature, extremism is a complex socio-political and legal phenomenon. That is why it has become the object of study by specialists in the field of philosophy, psychology, sociology, political science, and jurisprudence.

Since extremists turned out to be able to quickly change their own tactics and strategy, create stable groups, and adapt to legal anti-extremist measures, the problem remains of an in-depth scientific study of ways to combat extremist activities both at the national level and in the international arena.

In our opinion, the timely development of high-quality mechanisms to counter extremism is possible subject to an in-depth study of world practice in countering this illegal phenomenon, which has become the subject of our scientific search.

In the late 60s and early 70s, the world community was faced with the need to intensify counteraction to acts of international extremism and terrorism. After all, the geographical scope of extremist and terrorist activity has been expanded.

A natural reaction followed - cooperation between states in the fight against these negative phenomena intensified. Analyzing the existing practice of efforts of the world community in matters of countering acts of terror, we can distinguish four levels of this struggle: the global level under the auspices of the UN, the level of Europe under the auspices of the Council of Europe, the efforts of the G8 states and international cooperation of the CIS countries.

The direct activities of states in the field of international cooperation on countering extremism are based on generally recognized principles and norms of international law. The international fight against extremism dates back to Additional Protocol II of 1977 to the Geneva Conventions for the Protection of Victims of War of August 12, 1949, which are also aimed at protecting victims of non-international armed conflicts.

This document stipulates that: “any armed conflict of a non-international nature can be regarded as international extremism if its participants, who are in opposition to the government regime, do not comply with the generally recognized principles and norms of international law”.

However, “the Protocol does not apply to cases of internal disturbances and internal tensions, such as riots, isolated and sporadic acts of violence and other acts of a similar nature, since these do not constitute armed conflicts”.

Further, the fight against extremism was noted in the Declaration and Programs of Action, which were adopted at the UN World Conference on Human Rights on June 25, 1993 in Vienna. The latter established that: “acts, methods and practices of terrorism in all its forms and manifestations are activities aimed at the destruction of rights, freedoms and democracy, pose a threat to the territorial integrity and security of states and destabilize legitimate governments” [1].

In December 2008, the UN General Assembly adopted a resolution “The unacceptability of certain practices that contribute to the escalation of contemporary forms of racism, racial discrimination, xenophobia and related intolerance” [2].

The resolution condemns “propaganda and all organizations based on ideas of racial superiority or attempting to justify or promote racial hatred and discrimination in any form” and calls on states to “declare illegal and prohibit organizations and organized and all other propaganda activities that promote racial discrimination and incitement thereto, and to make participation in such organizations or activities an offense punishable by law.”

The fundamental distinctive features of international responsibility for various manifestations of extremist terrorist activities within the UN are:

“a) recognition of extremism (its individual forms) as a threat to international legality and order in the world;

b) insufficient development of the categorical apparatus, in particular, there is no generally accepted international legal definition of extremism and its forms;

c) the presence of legal mechanisms for bringing to responsibility for the most dangerous and widespread manifestations of extremism (mainly for terrorist activities, for violation of the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of a person and citizen, depending on his social, racial, national, religious and linguistic affiliation);

d) delay on the part of a number of UN member states in signing existing international conventions and protocols on countering extremism” [3].

Taking into account the norms of international law, all forms of extremism pose a threat to international security and require joint action by states to combat them. There is an urgent need to strengthen international legal cooperation between states in the field of combating extremism and terrorism, which are characterized as a threat to international, collective and national security and require special attention in the context of the fight against extremist crimes.

Back in 2003, the Parliamentary Assembly of the Council of Europe adopted resolution “Threats of extremist parties and movements to democracy in Europe” No. 1344, in which it defined extremism as one of the forms of political activity, openly or covertly rejects the principles of parliamentary democracy and partly establishes its own ideology, political practice and activities based on the principles of intolerance, exclusivity, xenophobia, anti-Semitism and ultra-nationalism.

The said resolution noted that in conditions of social discontent, extremism offers simple, stereotypical solutions as responses to the anxiety and uncertainty inherent in certain social groups in conditions of social change. At the same time, extremists place responsibility for existing difficulties on individual government officials or a certain part of the population [4].

An expression of the activation of states in the field of countering extremist and terrorist activities was the adoption of a number of international legal acts, the action of which was aimed at countering extremism, separatism and international terrorism through regional cooperation between states. In this regard, special mention should be made of the Declaration on the Establishment of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO).

The goals of the SCO are “strengthening mutual trust, friendship and good neighborliness between member states, encouraging effective cooperation between them in political, trade, economic, scientific, technical and other fields, joint efforts to maintain and ensure peace, security and stability in the region, building a new democratic , a just and rational political and economic international order; it is not an alliance directed against other states and regions, and adheres to the principle of openness” [5].

It is important to note that at the international level, such phenomena first received normative recognition through the concept of “extremism” precisely in the Shanghai Convention on Combating Terrorism, Separatism and Extremism of June 15, 2001.

Shanghai Convention in Art. 1 defined “extremism” as “any act aimed at forcibly seizing power or forcibly retaining power, as well as forcibly changing the constitutional system of the state, as well as a violent encroachment on public safety, including the organization of illegal armed groups or participation in them.”

The Convention provides that the Parties, in accordance with the provisions of the Convention itself, other international obligations, as well as taking into account their national legislation, cooperate in the field of preventing, identifying and suppressing international terrorism, separatism and extremism, for which they create central competent authorities, which, in particular , assist each other by exchanging information, fulfilling requests, operational-search activities, developing and taking measures to prevent and suppress international terrorism, separatism and extremism.

At the same time, the Convention attempted to distinguish the categories of “extremism” from “terrorism”. A separate significant aspect that must be taken into account when considering the issue of cooperation between states in the field of countering extremism and other threats to international and national security is that all member countries of the community are parties to the Collective Security Treaty, signed in Tashkent on May 15, 1992.

Also, we can observe a trend towards unification of the legislative framework of the member states of the Commonwealth in recent years. Let us note that such cooperation is expressed not only in the field of international security and the fight against terrorism, but also in all other areas related to the security of states.

One of the confirmations of the above is the adoption of numerous model laws and recommendations within the framework of the Interparliamentary Assembly of the CIS Member States.

The first document on the creation of a new organization to maintain collective security on the basis of the CIS was the Collective Security Treaty of May 15, 1992 after the collapse of the USSR.

This document determined that: “the participating states confirm the obligation to refrain from the use of force or the threat of force in interstate relations, and undertake to resolve all disagreements between themselves and with other states by peaceful means.”

In addition, according to Article 1 of the Treaty, “state parties will not enter into military alliances or take part in any groupings of states, as well as actions directed against another state party.”

The main characteristics of international responsibility for various manifestations of extremism and extremist activities within the Commonwealth of Independent States, as defined in the Collective Security Treaty of May 15, 1992, were the following:

“a) recognition of extremism as a threat to the collective and national security of the CIS member states;

b) the presence of a developed categorical apparatus, in particular, definitions of extremism, extremist organization and extremist materials;

c) development of legislation of the CIS member states on countering extremism on the basis of regulatory legal acts of the Russian Federation in this area;

d) the presence of a unified mechanism for interaction between law enforcement agencies of the CIS member states on issues of identifying, preventing and suppressing acts of extremism” [6].

In order to develop cooperation on countering terrorism and other manifestations of extremism, on August 26, 2005, the Council of Heads of State of the CIS adopted a decision on the Concept of cooperation between member states of the Commonwealth of Independent States in the fight against terrorism and other violent manifestations of extremism.

All CIS member states accept the Concept of cooperation in the fight against terrorism and other violent manifestations of extremism in accordance with their international obligations and national legislation in this area.

The concept is a system of views on the main directions and forms of cooperation in the fight against terrorism and extremism within the CIS and defines the goals, objectives and principles of such cooperation”.

Issues of combating extremism are also covered in the model law on countering extremism, adopted on May 14, 2009 at a meeting of the Interparliamentary Assembly of Member States of the Commonwealth of Independent States [7].

The peculiarity of this act is that it also distinguishes between extremism and extremist activity. In 2011, four Central Asian states (Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan and Turkmenistan) signed a Joint Action Plan in Ashgabat for the implementation of the UN Global Counter-Terrorism Strategy in Central Asia, pledging to jointly counter radicalism and terrorism in the region.

The Joint Action Plan for Central Asia is the first regional document aimed at organizing the fight against the threat of terrorism by applying a unified approach based on the UN Global Counter-Terrorism Strategy and strengthening international partnerships [8].

Another indicator of the rethinking of counter-terrorism in the region is the Plan of Action to Prevent Violent Extremism, published by the UN Secretary-General at the end of 2015. He calls on the international community to take concerted action.

The plan contains more than 70 recommendations addressed to Member States and the United Nations system aimed at preventing the further spread of violent extremism [9]. The plan also calls on governments to recognize that their own policies may increase radicalization [10].

An analysis of international law and the legislation of individual countries suggests that in democratic states the approach to understanding extremism is changing. The main documents of foreign states on ensuring national security condemn manifestations of violent extremism and propose persecution of members of relevant extremist groups.

This is stated, in particular, in the American strategy “Empowering local partners to prevent violent extremism in the United States”, the British strategy “Prevent Strategy”, as well as in the latest documents of the United Nations (UN) and its institutions.

At the same time, in all countries of Central Asia, the terms “extremism” and “violent extremism” are used as synonyms, although in Western expert circles they differ markedly (the first includes the entire range of measures and instruments, and the second is more concentrated on the physical and military components) [11].

In Resolution No. 68/127 of December 18, 2013, “Peace Against Violence and Extremism,” the UN General Assembly condemns targeted attacks against civilians, especially women and children, in particular regarding attacks by violent extremists; encourages states to unite in the fight against violent extremism in all its forms and manifestations, as well as against sectarian violence; calls on states to respect human and civil rights and freedoms, their protection, as well as adherence to the principle of the rule of law in the fight against violent extremism [12].

The UN Human Rights Council resolution No. 30/15 dated October 2, 2015 “Human Rights and Preventing and Combating Violent Extremism” states that: acts, methods and practices of violent extremism in all forms and manifestations are activities aimed at undermining the implementation of human rights and fundamental freedoms, violation of the territorial integrity and security of states and destabilization of legitimately formed authorities; the international community should take the necessary steps to strengthen cooperation to prevent and combat violent extremism, states are responsible for activities related to the prevention and suppression of violent extremism and terrorism in all forms and manifestations in the territories under their jurisdiction.

Such activities must be carried out in full compliance with the international legal obligations of states, as well as in compliance with due process of law and the principle of the rule of law [13].

On June 11-12, 2015, a Regional Summit on Countering Violent Extremism was held in Australia (Sydney), during which the Attorney General of Australia indicated that the problem of countering extremist propaganda, in particular on the Internet, cannot be solved by the efforts of one nation alone. Solving this global issue requires intensive cooperation between the states of the region based on trust and shared responsibility [14].

In modern conditions, extremism is a real threat to individuals, society and the state. However, it is necessary to counter this phenomenon in a comprehensive manner, taking into account all the problems that exist in society, as well as in interstate relations. All countries should maintain contacts with international organizations in order to exchange relevant information and experience.

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